

DETERMINATION OF THE OXIDATIVE STRESS BIOMARKERS OF 8-HYDROXYDEOXYGUANOSINE AND DITYROSINE IN GILLS, SKIN, DORSAL FIN, AND LIVER TISSUE OF ATLANTIC SALMON (*SALMO SALAR*) PARR

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Introduction

8-Hydroxydeoxyguanosine (8OHdG) and dityrosine (DIY) are specific biomarkers of DNA and protein damage from oxidative stress, respectively (Valavanidis, et al. 2009; Malencik, et al. 2003). Nowadays, 8OHdG analysis in fish is mostly performed with these specific kits/antibody methods (Oğuz, et al. 2018; Gyimah, et al. 2020; Alak, et al. 2017). However, the selectivity of ELISA in trace concentrations can be compromised from cross-reactivity with other co-occurring analogues, while simultaneous determination of 8OHdG and DIY with a single assay is currently not available. With this background, an extraction methodology tailored to UPLC®–ESI (electrospray)–MS/MS analysis was developed in the present study for the simultaneous determination of 8OHdG and DIY and was applied in tissue samples (skin, gills, dorsal fin, and liver) that were collected from Atlantic salmon parr individuals reared in an experimental recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) treated with peracetic acid.

Materials and Methods

The skin, gills, dorsal fin and liver were collected from 234 Atlantic salmon parr (4 x 234 = 936 samples) at the Tromsø Aquaculture Research Station in Kårvik, Norway (Mota, et al. 2022). The tissue samples were thawed in room temperature and a portion of ~100 mg of each tissue sample was transferred into a 15 mL PP tube. Samples were fortified with 15 µL of 1000 ng/mL isotope labeled IS-mixture followed by the addition of 600 µL MeOH containing 1% ammonium formate (w/v). Thereafter, the samples were vortex mixed (30 s) and ultrasonication (30 min) was performed followed by centrifugation (5 min, 3500 rpm). The supernatant was collected and transferred into a new 15 mL PP tube. Two different cleaning methods were tailored to the extraction protocol. Finally, the

extract was transferred for UPLC[®]-MS/MS analysis.

Results

The relative recoveries of 8OH DG and DIY were 101±11.1 % and 104±12.0 %, respectively, ensuring the accuracy of the extraction and quantification. The inter-day precision (method reproducibility, RSD %, N = 18) at the fortified concentration of 10 ng/mL were 5.62 and 5.18 % for 8OH DG and DIY, respectively. The chromatographic separation was carried out using a gradient elution program with a total run time of 5 min. The limits of detection (LODs) were 0.11 and 1.37 ng/g wet weight (w.w.) for 8OH DG and DIY, respectively. To demonstrate the applicability of the developed method, it was applied in 907 tissue samples that were collected from Atlantic salmon parr individuals reared in an experimental land-based recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) treated with peracetic acid. The detection rates of both target analytes were > 70% in the tissues, except from the low detection rate of 8OH DG reported in the liver samples (24%). Moreover, the possibility of using dorsal fin as an alternative matrix for the minimally invasive assessment of oxidative stress in Atlantic salmon parr was introduced.

Conclusions

A methodology tailored to UPLC[®]-MS/MS was developed for the determination of two oxidative stress biomarkers, 8OH DG and DIY, in gills, skin, dorsal fin, and liver tissue of Atlantic salmon parr. The method was applied successfully in 907 fish tissue samples from Atlantic salmon, and both biomarkers were detected in most samples. Moreover, correlations of the biomarkers across tissues were uncovered, introducing the possibility of using dorsal fin as an alternative matrix for the minimally invasive assessment of oxidative stress in Atlantic salmon parr.

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